

ISic1301

I.Sicily inscription 1301

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140793

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Ἰουλία □ Α[ῖ]λια-
3. ν[ή] □ ἔζησε
4. ἔτη κ □ μ [ῆ] ν (ας) □ β',
5. [ή] μέρ (ας) □ κε', Α[ῖ]-
6. λιανός θυγ[α]-
7. τρι □ εὐσεβεστά (τη) .
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492906

EDCS 39101671

PHI 140793

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0478 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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